

In vitro antioxidant activity of some newly synthesized 1,2,4-triazolophenyl-quinoline derivatives

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Abstract : A series of 1,2,4-triazolophenylquinoline derivatives were synthesized by cyclisation method. Synthesized molecules were characterized by spectral and elemental analysis. These newly synthesized molecules were screened for their *in vitro* antioxidant activity. Some of the synthesized compounds showed potent antioxidant activity.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazolophenylquinoline, antioxidant, spectrophotometer, ascorbic acid.

Results and discussion

All the synthesized compounds were screened for their nitric oxide scavenging activity by use of spectrophotometer. Some of the synthesized compounds (compounds containing Cl, CH₃, OCH₃ group) shown same potent nitric oxide scavenging, when compared with standard drug ascorbic acid (Table 1). All the data were collected in triplicate method. So from this experiment, it proves that these newly synthesized compounds can be scavengers of free radicals. Hence these compounds can be used as antioxidants by some modification.

Materials and method : All the chemicals and solvents which were used are of AR grade. Melting points were determined in open capillary method and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G. IR

spectra were recorded by spectrophotometer (FTIR-8400S, Shimadzu) using KBr disc method. ¹H NMR spectra was recorded by Bruker DRX-300 MHz FT NMR with low and high temperature facility (-90 °C - +80 °C). The solvents used were CDCl₃ and DMF for ¹H NMR and graph of the specific samples were obtained. Systronic spectrophotometer was used for determination of absorbance.

Procedure : The synthesized compounds 1,2,4-triazolophenylquinoline derivatives (Fig. 1) were prepared and purified as in reported method⁸. Then the compounds were tested for their antioxidant activity. Sreejayan *et al.*⁹ method was followed for performing the experiment. NO exists primarily as NO₂ and NO₃ in biological systems. Its measurement can be a useful tool in estimat-

Table 1

Drug code	R	Molecular formula	Mass (g/mol)	Antioxidant activity : NO scavenging activity				
				Concentration (µg/ml)				
				5	10	20	50	100
A	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂	292.23	0.938	0.964	0.712	0.883	1.239
B	Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₃	281.73	1.243	1.246	1.248	1.251	1.255
C	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃	247.29	0.841	0.846	0.851	0.903	0.907
D	Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrN ₃	326.19	0.957	0.974	0.991	1.044	1.127
E	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃	261.32	1.126	1.146	1.162	1.177	1.180
F	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	277.32	1.224	1.226	1.232	1.252	1.303
Blank	-	-	-	1.214	1.214	1.214	1.214	1.214
Ascorbic Acid	-	C ₆ H ₈ O ₆	176.124	1.350	1.406	1.664	1.808	1.944

- A = 7-Nitro-5-phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
 B = 7-Chloro-5-phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
 C = 5-Phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
 D = 7-Bromo-5-phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
 E = 7-Methyl-5-phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
 F = 7-Methoxy-5-phenyl-3,3a-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoline
- A = R-NO₂, B = R-Cl, C = R-H, D = R-Br, E = R-CH₃,
 F = R -OCH₃

Fig. 1

ing NOS activity. The principle of this assay is based on the measurement of NO₂ produced in the sample during a time reaction compared with a heat-inactivated control sample. Spectrophotometric quantization of nitrite using Griess reagents is straight forward and sensitive method. Different concentrations of drug solution prepared in (μg/ml) were taken. Then from the stock solution of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), 0.5 ml of the solution was taken in different test tube. Then to each test tube 2 ml of sodium nitroprusside was added and this mixture solution was incubated for 3 h. Then to each mixture solution 0.5 ml

Griess reagent was added. Then absorbance was immediately measured at 540 nm. The increase in absorbance shows the increase in NOS activity.

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